

Measuring the de Broglie wavelength of electrons using Thomson e/m tube

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Abstract

The Thomson e/m experiment laid the foundation of the first atomic particle and for once proved the existence of discrete charged particles, now known as electrons. This work aims at studying the wave nature of electrons by measuring their de Broglie wavelengths. The wavelength was obtained from two different facets, namely, the electric field and the magnetic field, and then it has been shown that the two values are in agreement with each other to an order of 10^{-11} m.

1 Introduction

J.J. Thomson first measured the specific charge (e/m) of the electron in 1897 by analyzing the its motion in a cross electric and magnetic field. It was Thompson's hypothesis of the existence of electron like particles that lead to the concept of the first atomic model.

Figure 1: Schematic of the cathode ray tube

The apparatus shown in Figure 1. consists of an electron gun fitted inside a glass tube filled with helium gas. This gun has a cathode filament and a nearby anode which can be set to a potential which is positive relative to the cathode. The electrons are thermionically released from the cathode and accelerate towards the anode. The anode, however, contains a slit which lets a fraction of the electrons into the larger volume of the glass tube. A pair of circular Helmholtz coils are wound and arranged such that the uniform magnetic field is perpendicular to the travelling electrons. Due to presence of this magnetic field, the electrons released from the slit travel in a circular loop across the tube and reach the anode. The electrons collide with the helium atoms on their way and a greenish halo is visible.

2 Theory

2.1 de Broglie wavelength from electric field

An electron accelerated through the positive anode potential V_a gains a kinetic energy of

$$\frac{p^2}{2m_e} = eV_a \quad (1)$$

Where p is the momentum and m_e is the mass of the electron.

$$p = \sqrt{2m_e eV_a} \quad (2)$$

Thus the de Broglie wavelength of the electrons turns out to be

$$\lambda_e = \frac{h}{\sqrt{2m_e eV_a}} \quad (3)$$

2.2 de Broglie wavelength from magnetic field

For the electron moving in a circular orbit, the centripetal force is supplied by the Lorentz force

$$\frac{mv^2}{r} = ev \times B \quad (4)$$

Where r is the radius of the electron loop. Since the magnetic field is perpendicular to the travelling electrons, this simplifies to

$$\frac{mv^2}{r} = evB \quad (5)$$

$$p = erB \quad (6)$$

The magnetic field from the Helmholtz coils is in turn given by

$$B = \frac{8}{\sqrt{125}} \frac{\mu_0 NI}{R} \quad (7)$$

Table 1: The data collected and the corresponding wavelengths

Accelerating Voltage (V)	Diameter (m)	Wavelength from Eq(3) (pm)	Wavelength from Eq(9) (pm)
100	0.062	122.77	130.00
120	0.070	112.07	115.14
140	0.075	103.76	107.46
160	0.081	97.06	99.50
180	0.090	91.51	89.55
200	0.095	86.81	84.84

Where N is the number of turns in the coil, I is the current in the coil and R is the radius of the coil. Therefore, Eq (6) becomes

$$p = \frac{4}{\sqrt{125}} \frac{\mu_0 e d N I}{R} \quad (8)$$

Where $d = 2r$ is the diameter of the electron loop. Thus the de Broglie wavelength of the electrons turns out to be

$$\lambda_e = \frac{\sqrt{125}}{4} \frac{hR}{\mu_0 e d N I} \quad (9)$$

We measure the variables on the RHS and calculate the value of the de Broglie wavelength of the electrons. To cross-check our values, we do the same with Eq (3).

2.3 Relativistic consideration

From Eq (2), the velocity of the electrons is of the order $v \sim 10^6 \text{ ms}^{-1}$. The Lorentz factor turns out to be $\gamma = 1.00005$.

Therefore, percentage increase in the mass of an electron is 0.005%. Thus, relativistic effects can be neglected.

3 Experimental details

The number of turns in the Helmholtz coils are $N = 160$.

The radius of the Helmholtz coils are $R = 0.14 \text{ m}$.

The current in the coil is kept constant at $1A$; higher currents can burn the loop.

The standard value of e is $1.602 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$.

The standard value of the mass of an electron is $m_e = 9.109 \times 10^{-31} \text{ kg}$.

One has to wait several minutes for the cathode to heat up. When the beam appears, the voltage is increased and the corresponding value of the diameter of the electron loop is noted in Table 1.

The greatest source of error in this experiment is the change in momentum of the electrons. Firstly, the non-uniformity of the accelerating field caused by the hole in the anode causes the velocity of the electrons to be slightly less than their theoretical value. Second, the electron beam colliding with the helium atoms scatters the beam and further decreases their velocity. The experiment was conducted in a darkened box for better viewing.

4 Conclusion

It can be concluded from the data in Table 1 that the correct values of the de Broglie wavelengths of electrons were obtained since the values from the two different equations are in agreement to an order of 10^{-11} m. Thus, it can be said that with this experiment one can also investigate the wave-nature of electron using Thomson's e/m apparatus. This leads to a comprehensive analysis of the wave-particle duality of electrons in a single experiment.